

Corrigenda to “On the Reflex of Irish / \tilde{v} / in Old Norse” in *JEGP* vol. 124, no. 3,
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Errata corrigere

Cover: for “Nicolai Edjar” read “Nicolai Egjar”.

Passim: replace the appropriate IPA symbols (lowercase for uppercase) in the headings.

Passim: I denote the nasalized bilabial fricative as / \tilde{v} /, as the appropriate IPA symbol β could not be printed with the tilde.

p. 275, line 14: rebreak before ‘/’ so that ‘/gawən’/’ appears as one unit.

p. 278. 15–16: for “a phonemic contrast /vn ~ mn/ in ON” read “a phonemic contrast /vn/ vs. /mn/ in ON”.

p. 283, 8: rebreak “*kjall-(l)-ámur*” as “*kjall-(l)ámur*”.

p. 283, 20: for “within ON.” read “within ON (see Table 1).”

p. 283, 24–5: delete “The examples are (ON inflectional endings within parentheses).” The text as it stands provides no clue as to where the examples are cited. They are cited in Table 1.

p. 284: The heading of the table should of course not be taken to suggest that (-y-) is an inflectional ending.

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